

Linguocultural Aspect of Clothes in English and Uzbek Languages

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Abstract:

This article is devoted to the study of analyses of cognitive linguo-cultural aspect of the clothes in English and Uzbek languages. The changes in the social and cultural life of the people caused to the extinction of some words among nations. Clothes considered as the conductor in history and culture of the people, the attires defines the nationality, mentality, authentic tastes and attitudes of the people. Study of lingua-cultural aspect of words definitely connected with the culture of people. In this paper information about the clothes of two cultures show mentality and traditional peculiarities of two nations.

Key words: Clothing, material, culture, mentality, indicator, significant.

INTRODUCTION. Clothing is a significant part of a person's culture, and one of the crucial indicators of his separation from the natural word along with speech and name. The diversity of clothing items defines gender, age, social, regional and ethnic groups. Besides that, the role of clothes is very crucial in both English and Uzbek cultures, and it reflects various lingua-cultural aspects connected with the identity, tradition, and social norms.

The culture of each nation is reflected in language. It is found in the facts, such as the appearance and disappearance of words marked with their realities, and abundance of special names that reflect the interest of social groups and climatic conditions [1].

Language as component of spiritual culture holds a special place, as a necessary means and conditions for the development and operation of the other components of culture. Language is one of the specific components of any ethnic culture, it is most clearly manifested the, otherness, the

difference of different cultures: “Language performs the function of ethnic characteristic only on the properties of this particular nation [2].

Language through the words can show the culture of nation. It means words, household words, especially, clothes words can describe the life of people and introduce with mentality[3].

The study of traditional clothes is the scientific significance and history of language from the position. traditional clothes considered as a source of learning the ethnic history of the people and their culture, language, relationship with other people. Clothes especially traditional are not something static or frozen. The style of clothes formed historically for centuries and developing continuously in all the way of the existence of the people. Traditional clothes are key factors for learning the ethnic history of other nations all over the world.

In English, terms for clothes often classified according to their function or design (e.g. casual , formal, outerwear, accessories). Fashion in Western cultures is often associated with individuality, personal expression and trends. Clothes also used to express markers of professional status, social identity, and in some cases, political statements as well. Words like suit, jeans, dress, or uniform each of these carry specific connotations and cultural meanings. For instance, a business suit represents professionalism and is often tied to formal or corporate environments, while jeans signifies casual wear, used in everyday life[4].

In Uzbekistan, traditional clothing has deep roots in history, often identifies ethnic identity, the different styles within regions, and societal roles. The usage of terms in Uzbek language for clothing often carries a sense of cultural heritage.

Words such as do’ppi (traditional hat), atlas (a type of silk used in national dresses), or khalat (robe) not only describe clothing but also communicate the wear’s background, such as region or professional status. The khan-atlas or adras fabrics are considered as the national identity and still used in the ceremonies and celebrations .

In terms of the symbolism and identity each clothes of both nations has its own function and specialty. Clothing in English – speaking world often symbolizes one’s status, profession, or role in the society.

For example: A white wedding dress symbolizes purity and tradition. Black -tie attire signals high formality and is tied to prestigious events, such clothes identifies the social status of the person. While there are some specific items like the kilts in Scottish tradition symbolize regional and family heritage.

In Uzbek culture, traditional Uzbek clothing also carries deep symbolic meanings. Woman’s dresses which are made of atlas (silk) often represent femininity and are worn during festivals or some occasions like weddings, reflecting social customs and traditional values. do’ppi, a four- sided skullcap, represents cultural pride and is worn by both men and women during ceremonies or daily life, with different styles indicating different regions. The chakman, considered as a traditional outer garments, symbolize modesty and respect, particularly in rural areas[5].

Global influences and modernization have affected significantly to the development of clothing both in English and Uzbek cultures. Western clothing has been seriously shaped by globalization fashion and designer labels are becoming common, blending cultural boundaries. While traditional clothes still kept their own status in certain celebrations, but global trends has changed heavily everyday wear of people. However, in Uzbek culture modern styles of clothing like jeans, shirts and blouses have become popular in urban areas, traditional garments are still prevalent, especially during festivals , weddings, and other cultural events. The blend of modernity and tradition shows how globalization influence local fashion while preserving cultural identity. Even words from

English fashion like brand (brand), have become common among Uzbek people, illustrating the merging of cultures.

Religious and Ethical aspects also considered as one of the most crucial factor in clothing. As a predominantly Muslim country, modesty in clothing is emphasized, particularly among women. According to Islamic standards traditional clothing is often designed to cover the body, though variations exist depending on regional practices and degrees of religious adherence. Religion has influenced the style of clothing in English-Speaking countries. Such as head covering among Muslim or Jewish women or clergy uniforms in Christianity. Besides that the concept of gender distinction between men's and women's attire become prominent in English-Speaking societies. In Uzbekistan Gender distinctions in clothing are more pronounced, especially in rural or traditional settings. Men's and women's garments often follow conventional norms, with women wearing modest, colorful dress and headscarves (hijabs in some cases) and men wearing long robes during certain occasions. However, the adoption to the more Westernized fashion become common among the citizens of urban areas.

Using proverbs and Idioms according to the attire of the person is common among the population of both Nations. In English language "Don't judge a book by its cover" suggests that appearance (including clothing) can be deceiving. "Dressed to kill" means dressing extremely fashionable or striking way. We can see some other proverbs and idioms in Uzbek language as well. For instance, "Kiyimiga qarab kutib, aqliga qarab kuzatadilar"/"They welcome you by your clothes, and observe you off by your intelligence", it means that both appearance and intelligent is important in social interactions.

CONCLUSION. The aim of this thesis was to understand the way clothes are viewed and described in both English and Uzbek languages reflects deeper cultural values, societal roles' and historical heritages. While individuality, trends and professional identity have been emphasized by English – Speaking culture, Uzbek culture maintains stronger connection to tradition, regional identity, and ceremonial significance, though both of them are influenced by the forces of modernization and globalization.

REFERENCES

1. Rustamovna A. D. Technology Of Teaching Languages //JournalNX. – 2020. – C. 180-183.
2. Rustamovna A. D., Xasanovna A. S. Modern pedagogical technologies as a means of improving the quality of education. – C. 176.
3. Alaudinova D. Theoretical approach of oral communication competency //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 3/S. – С.147-151.
4. Luria, A., 1976. Cognitive Development: Its Cultural and Social Foundations. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, –P.210.
5. Ferguson, C., (1959). Diglossia: Language in culture and society. Word, 1(2): –P.325-340.
6. Agaev, A., (1968). Language functions as an ethnic trait. Language and Society. Nauka Press, – P.250.
7. Telia, V., 1999. The basic postulates of linguistics. A Philology and Culture: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference, –P. 30-33.
8. M.I. Gadoeva, D.Ziyaeva. (2023). O'zbek va ingliz tillarida nutq fe'llarining funksional-kognitiv tadqiqi. Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 263–265. Retrieved from <https://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/1064>

9. Ibragimovna, G. M. (2023, May). So'z yasalishi talqini. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 35-39).
10. Ibragimovna, G. M., & Baxtiyorovna, Y. L. (2023, May). Olam manzarasi tasvirida somatizmlarning roli. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 40-44).
11. Ibragimovna, G. M., & Nargiza, Q. (2023, May). Matal va maqollarda somatik birliklar ifodasi. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 25-28).
12. Gadoeva, M. I., & Mohinabegim, Y. (2023, May). Causes, goals and conditions of euphemization of speech. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 20-24).
13. Gadoyeva, M. I., & Vodgorova, L. B. (2023). Ingliz va o'zbek tillari topishmoqlar tarkibida somatizmlarning qo'llanilishi. Scientific aspects and trends in the field of scientific research, 1(9), --B.236-241.
14. Gadoyeva, M. I. (2023). Ingliz tilida soz yasash usullari. Scientific aspects and trends in the field of scientific research, 1(9), --B.266-270.
15. Gadoyeva, M. I., & Charos, S. (2023). Ingliz va ozbek tillarida nutq fellari. scientific aspects and trends in the field of scientific research. B.230-235.
16. Gadoeva, M. I. (2023). O'zbek tilida so'z yasalishiga doir tasavvurlar. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, --B.186-192.